

provided only if the student requests them through free-form, user-generated commands. The system then shows the requested clinical assessment findings as high-definition photos, sounds and/or text. The student determines whether the assessment finding is normal or abnormal and reports it, resembling a CS session. Diverse patient profiles have been included in the tool, such as BIPOC, LGBTQ+ and other marginalised populations, to expose students to a wider range of assessment findings than would typically be available in pre-clinical settings. This is critically important for developing a culturally responsive and inclusive tool that promotes socially responsible education.

3 | WHAT LESSONS WERE LEARNED?

NLP AI was successfully leveraged to develop a clinical skills digital solution, and the multiprofessional team was the keystone in the accomplishment. Student feedback collected during alpha testing indicated that they appreciated the opportunity for repeated practice and the use of multimedia to learn CS concepts. Medical programme faculty endorsed the innovation and expressed interest in the potential benefits of student performance diagnostics and customised evaluations.

This innovation has many long-term benefits that will continue to be valuable beyond the COVID-19 pandemic. Students can use this innovation to practice what they learn during in-person CS sessions

by customising their experience to their learning needs and receiving immediate feedback on their performance. Ongoing development of this innovation will allow students to explore various pathologies and patient presentations through different media, enabling students to use cognitive patterns that more closely align with in-person practice. The team plans to explore future opportunities including conversational history taking, voice-to-text AI and richer multimedia, such as video and 3D imaging.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors do not have any conflict of interest to declare.

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Innovating medical education—Bringing the clinical environment online

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1 | WHAT PROBLEMS WERE ADDRESSED?

As a medical student, transitioning from university- to hospital-based learning is a highly anticipated rite of passage. It's a unique experience that challenges students to think critically and practically apply the knowledge they have gained thus far. Unfortunately, the COVID-19 pandemic has changed all this. Not having that first in-person patient interaction can significantly impact a student's ability to consolidate knowledge and engage in experiential and peer assisted learning. As final-year students who had the unique experience of pre-COVID clinical experience and online education, it

was our goal to reflect on our experiences and simulate the clinical environment for new students.

2 | WHAT WAS TRIED?

Using a process called design thinking, our first step was to empathise with the students and understand how their experiences were different to ours. Using this insight and facilitated by academic staff, we synthesised a range of near-peer-assisted clinical learning aids in the form of a clinical guidebook, podcasts and a clinical exam skills teaching

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video. The guidebook and podcasts covered high-yield clinical scenarios and sample history vignettes with accompanying guidance on how to present the history. We also included tips on approaching patients and taking histories that we had gained during our clinical experience. The neonatal examination video consisted of a head-to-toe examination of a newborn baby supplemented by a voiceover explaining the steps and the relevance of each section. We will be actively looking for student feedback to further refine these learning aids.

3 | WHAT LESSONS WERE LEARNED?

To design appropriate content, we reflected on our own experiences and what tools were most beneficial to our learning, including learning opportunities that are unique to the clinical environment. We realised the importance of experiential learning in how much you can gain from observation and interacting with patients. These personal interactions are crucial in solidifying concepts learned in the classroom and grounding knowledge in practice. Additionally, we realised that virtual learning means that students miss out on the passive learning obtained from face-to-face interactions with peers, in addition to the

social support provided from classmates. Peer-assisted learning is a hidden asset of medical education and through discussion and collaboration further insight and knowledge can be obtained.

This was our first experience as educators rather than students. As a physician, dedication to life-long learning is an essential component of one's career, and through our participation in this project, we were able to take that first step into teaching. If anything, COVID-19 has forced medical schools and clinical educators to be creative and innovative in designing and delivering medical curriculum. Although many new avenues of teaching were designed during the pandemic, their application is likely to still be beneficial when clinical placement practice returns to normal. As medical students who have recently engaged in similar clinical modules, we have the unique insight and recent memory of our first hospital experience, and thus, our ability to engage these students in peer assisted learning can provide additional benefits to the standard curriculum.

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Developing medical artificial intelligence leaders: International university consortium approach

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1 | WHAT PROBLEM WAS ADDRESSED?

Machine learning applications are increasingly used in medicine. The demand for 'augmented doctors,'¹ or 'enhanced physicians', that is, physicians capitalising rather than opposing incoming technology, has been recognised. However, teaching medical Artificial Intelligence is challenging, especially in already oversaturated medical curricula with most medical schools lacking Artificial Intelligence expertise.

To help medical students become 'augmented doctors', an international collaborative educational project, the GAME-TEI (Global Alliance of Medical Excellence-Transnational Educational Initiative) (<https://www.game-med.net/tei>), planned its 'summer school' themed *Artificial Intelligence in Medicine and Medical Education* at the University of Bologna, Italy in July 2020. The COVID-19 pandemic led

to a rapid transformation into an online course involving medical students from nine countries.

2 | WHAT WAS TRIED?

The international online medical Artificial Intelligence summer school ran a 6-week asynchronous pre-program followed by 3 days of live workshops. Forty-five medical students from representative medical schools (Asia-Pacific 18, Europe 20 and Canada 7) participated. Prior Artificial Intelligence experience was a desirable factor as it was originally intended as a 1-week intensive course. The online format allowed expanded student numbers and inclusion of Artificial Intelligence novice participants as well as a longer duration and a sequence of elements that better supported learning.

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